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Fostering Fair Data Practices in Europe

INFORMATION SHEET

RESEARCHERS

Persistent identifiers

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Using and publishing research outputs in a digital environment is not always simple if you want to be a trustworthy researcher. One challenge is **link-rot**: the fact that resources on the World Wide Web are moved over time, thereby invalidating references from outside to such resources. Another problem for researchers is **content drift**. This happens when the content behind a link changes.

To mitigate these problems, the FAIR principles call for the managed use of **PIDs: Persistent Identifiers**. Important properties of these identifiers are that they are guaranteed to continue existing (persistent), that they are globally only in use to identify a single resource (unique), and that there is a well-defined way to locate the actual resource based on the identifier (resolvable).

The researcher and the PID

Researchers as end users are usually dependent on what the services (software, data management, curation services etc.) offer regarding data processing, lifecycle management and publication HOURS. **Metadata formats, the quality of reference metadata, version management, securing integrity, structural metadata and PID minting and allocation are all products of the services used.** It is therefore good to be engaged also in planning the use of persistent identifiers with your data stewards and presenting your use cases to the service providers. From the researcher's point of view, there are two different PID contexts and the contexts can serve as different use cases. We will discuss two use cases below. In both of them consistent use of identifiers and PIDs is relevant and helpful to your work especially in the long run.

Making your work findable and possible to cite

The first use case is the **visibility of your work and outputs**. When reporting on your work to funders and when publishing outputs, a basic level of FAIRness and PID use is sufficient to enable findability and simple citation. What is needed is output registration with core descriptive metadata. This is the context of what is usually called *research information* (sometimes referred to as current research information). The most common and useful PIDs for this are the **research output DOI** and the **ORCID for the creator(s)/contributor(s)**. There are also other PID systems available to identify other kinds of entities to help further linking of information, such as organisations or protocols. Funders and employers might for instance require linking to some other contextual reference data like lists of grants, funders and affiliated organisations. This kind of information is becoming more important, but the actual data quality is dependent on the functionalities each service provides. If the services used for dataset publication or reporting don't require PIDs or don't offer reference (meta)datasets or integration with PIDs for these kinds of things, it is difficult for the researcher to provide this information in an unambiguous way.

Managing your research process

The other use case for PIDs is the **management of the research data itself**. Here the PIDs can have different functions: (a) creating deep FAIR research datasets as *research outputs*, where all individual data elements are machine accessible or (b) when managing and documenting the actual workflow and data and related information *during research* to ensure reproducibility of research results.

Assessing and planning the use of PIDs might be different depending on which aspect is in focus and is **best done by the researcher in collaboration with the data steward** who can present different solutions or ways to use PIDs. This also requires that you, together, decide on where the focus is put and what is good enough regarding for instance versioning,

reproducibility or machine actionability. This is better validated prior to the start of the research, and then checked at regular intervals during the research. The sustainability of identifiers should also be evaluated both during the active research period and after the project.

What should you give a PID?

Regarding **machine accessibility** there are different options depending on how developed data management and the domain infrastructure is and what is feasible and best serves the purposes of the research community. Usually there needs to be good semantic interoperability (see the document about [semantic interoperability](#)) in place before machine actionability can be put in place. Panel F in figure 1 shows a situation where the data is “Deep FAIR” and accessible for both machines and humans on a data element level. In these kinds of solutions the data elements are curated so that the integrity of individual objects, as well as creation of subsets, is ensured and sustainable. Your research community should agree upon the appropriate depth of FAIRness of the data. Keep in mind that applying restrictions on machine accessible data elements (panel D in figure 1 below) requires more extensive interoperability both legally and technically than open access cases, because one also has to create a way for identifying the users, their roles and access rights in an interoperable and automatic way before this can be implemented.

Data as increasingly FAIR Digital Objects

Figure 1 Different degrees of FAIR. Source: Mons et al 2017. We refer to “F” as “Deep FAIR”.

You can also use persistent and unique identifiers for supporting the creation of provenance metadata (provenance basically means 'how this came to be'), for instance by creating PIDs for sensors, instruments or workflows. Metadata and other requirements have to be defined by the research community when planning the information architecture and processes, but remember to look outside your own domain to find good practices with the help of your data stewards.

When PIDs are used to identify digital objects during the research, they support workflows and automation in metadata creation and machine actionable metadata at earlier stages of the data lifecycle, for instance see this reference. Metadata that is collected earlier and in an automated fashion like this is more likely to be complete and correct and may save time, as compared to when it needs to be recovered from scattered notes before data publication, which may be very time consuming and rushed due to nearing publication deadlines. These PIDs can act as anchor points in the data lifecycle. Code and software should also be considered as FAIR data objects. You can link or wrap PIDs, for instance, source data, software and outputs, to support the reproducibility of your research. PIDs can also be used in different ways when publishing actionable research outputs, thus supporting reproducibility. Documenting the research process and data provenance creates needs for identifying workflows. The Protocols service offers PIDs for protocols. The Common Workflow Language (CWL) is a way to wrap the research process and it can also include manual activities. There are different nascent ways of describing and structuring information about the processes and outputs of research, relevant ways among these are the Research Object Crate and on a higher level the RAiD.

Dos

Rather than defining new PIDs for an entity, be it a dataset, a piece of software, or a data type, or any term or item you want to represent, you should always first check whether a PID already exists.

As PIDs are a central element in creating FAIR data and ensuring registration of credits and scientific reproducibility, it is worthwhile spending some time and effort on exploring different solutions and options at an early stage of the research lifecycle and with the support of professional data stewards.

Actively present your use cases to service providers to improve the services to meet the needs of the research community.

So use PIDs whenever available also when citing, reporting and referencing things (terms, concepts, persons, organisations, publications, grants, data and sources, software and instruments) that have PIDs.

Don'ts

It is NOT recommended that the researcher or any individual person is the PID owner, but this, as well as management, should be governed in a sustainable way. It is better if the PID owner is an organisational body that can administer the curation and manage the costs over time.

Use PIDs mindfully and plan their use. Remember that **a published PID is a promise**. Large amounts of zombie PIDs (broken links and unmaintained metadata) would corrupt the whole system in the long run. There are always costs that someone has to take care of over time, when a PID is minted and published. Not only keeping the PID alive, but also taking care of the information behind the PID.

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